

TRANSLATION THEORY, PROBLEMS AND SOLUTIONS

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Abstract. Translation is vitally important for all languages in academic life like a language for the nation. So, several works have been done to contribute for the translating issues since still it has some problems to solve. The article includes some translational problems and it demonstrates solutions to those problems. Moreover, it illustrates some methods of translation in science of dictionary.

Keywords: text, translation, audio, sample, scientific popular method, experiment, computer, concept, press releases, news reports, scientific reports, instructions for use, instructions for use, descriptions of inventions, contracts, educational texts, art, literature, essays, biographies, novels, short stories, all of poetry forms.

INTRODUCTION

Most of the researchers of translation theory interpret the text as in the original language agree that it is necessary to fully understand. In our opinion, text and text any of which apply to all types of samples and occur during translation it is necessary to classify the possible source text types for use in the task. Such a classification in computer training with the help of exercises with texts to translators the function of elements or features observed in the content and structure of the source text should allow understanding. Based on this functional concept, they themselves they can choose translation strategies that are appropriate for the specific translation they are working on. In addition, synchronic translation by developing a model for selecting such texts based on the classification it is necessary to clarify the criteria for the selection of texts for teaching. At the same time, it is necessary to take into account the characteristics of speech, because ST (simultaneous translation) is directly oral as well as it is a form of communication. The following features of oral speech with consecutive translation closely related. Speech form (the difference of sound vibrations, one sound from another makes it possible to distinguish) also describes oral speech. Another tone of speech is the audience may be accepted differently. So, a very loud, intense voice of listeners can cause an unpleasant reaction. Loudness to the listener's perception also affects and adapts to different situations. Intonation is important in oral speech.

MATERIALS AND METHODS

It should be noted that the texts classification from the point of view of translation reflects the translator's skills in working with the text serves to develop discursive skills. Including informative text popular science written to inform the reader about a specific event is determined to be styled text. It is usually found in magazines, scientific or historical books, in autobiographies and manuals. Informative texts are basic to the reader and they are unique that allows you to easily find information and understand the main topic features. Authors of reference texts help readers find information quickly and efficiently they use different structures to help.

Translation has become a part of linguistics. This is the relationship between languages helped establish the regulatory rules and the similarity between them and identified the differences. The influence of linguistics even on the types of translation in linguistic communication including

marking based on differences and functional capabilities of languages received Translation interacts with different fields of linguistics. In one sense, it is related to general linguistics: syntax, semantics and morphology. Other on the other hand, it interacts with stylistics, sociolinguistics and psycholinguistics, in other fields such as comparative studies, bilingualism, and second language education became an important source for linguistics.

Carrying out work in the field of translation careful study of language units in foreign languages selected for linguistic and cultural analysis is of great importance in the process. Also, understand the difference between cultures to get it, it is necessary to understand and study the mentality of the people in the language of the original text. Lexical, grammatical, and stylistic methods are in place in accordance with translation norms improving the quality of translation. We understand that the culture of a certain nation is reflected in the language spoken by that nation. Not only the language and culture of the people today's lifestyle, but also the national, historical, religious culture is reflected.

RESEARCH AND DISCUSSION

The issue of translation from one language to another is one of the most important issues since the beginning of languages and their study. Because the development of a language depends on other languages. During the stages of language development, we can say that it interacts with other languages, acquires some words and can present some words.

In the translation process of any language, as well as when translating from English to Uzbek or vice versa from Uzbek to English, translators may face various problems. They are the most common cultural concepts and we cannot translate them. Instead, you can choose the equivalent of these words, or the next problem is that some words are not equivalent to traditional names, it is enough to give them a definition.

Below we found it necessary to present some translation problems and their approximate solutions based on a table:

№	Problem	Solution
1	Terms which describe customs, traditions, manners that are difficult to have equivalent in languages. For example: “hatna to’yi” or “sunnat to’yi”, “aqiqa to’yi” which are commonly used in uzbek language however they are not existed in English language	A good solution to this kind of a problem could be to give definitions for these terms that is to give all the features of these occasions and the activities in order to have correct imagination.
2	Some terms can not be given in translational dictionaries because of not having their equivalents in the foreign language	A good way to find out these words to have a good definitional dictionary. However, a good dictionary have to be written down
3	Some items like traditional items (xontaxta, yostiq, so’ri, sandal, tok, and many others) need to have long definition to have right view and learner	Good remedy for this issue is to give picture dictionary as well as to give a good definition to the given terms

	should be aware of the usage of the words.	
4	The translation of certain stereotypes or explaining the translation of concepts related to certain mentalities to the owners of other mentalities complicates the translation process a little.	We can say that giving definitions is an approximate solution to this problem. However, the time-consuming nature of definitions creates another problem of translation. Clearly, a better solution to these problems is still needed

CONCLUSION

Folklore in each language genres, proverbs, phrases, in that language, it is important to preserve and study the most of the people who communicate it is an important folk oral heritage. The task of this field is through language it is the ability to reflect the culture of the people that has been formed to this day. Culture serves as the basis of language and culture. First of all in culture the concept of this universe and man are closely related to each other increases. Every person in the society has his mother tongue with the culture of his people since childhood absorbs it. All subtle aspects of the national culture belong to this nation will be reflected in the language. In conclusion, it can be said that linguistic and cultural aspects of communication important in processes and in transferring information and ideas from one environment to another plays a role and everyone should consider these aspects and translation, writing and speaking should get acquainted with them. in some cases the reader's or the listener's an error that causes his displeasure and non-acceptance of the material delivered to him or lack of confusion or in other cases it leads to unpleasant results. In the course of our research, we witnessed that the role of language and culture is incomparable in literary translation.

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